

Study the Socio-Economic Spatial Regarding Livestock Development in Balochistan: Ways and Prospects

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Abstract

So as to determine demographic information about livestock management, the present study was designed. Seventy (70) respondents were selected by using by multi-stage sampling in the study areas. A descriptive sort of research designed used so that obtained the insight as awareness factors of the respondents at field level. The results indicated that majority of the respondents perceived that they have facilities of metallic roads (64.00%) majority of the respondents (90%) were married, while Brahvi speaking were 27.14% of the total sample size. Majority of the respondents (31.42%) had families with up to 5 members, and 17.14 % of the respondents were responsible to manage families. Majority (47.18%) was educated up to primary school level, 14.36% could reach middle school, and 5.13% achieved matriculation. Majority (55.71%) of the respondents had income up to 5000 rupees that majority of the respondents (58.57 %) had started livestock farming more than 10 years ago, while 17.14 percent of the respondents had started livestock farming during last 10 years. Majority of the respondents (74.28%) lived in katcha earthen house. Majority of the respondents (80%) had pit latrine at their residential accommodation. Majority of the respondents (55.71%) used tube well water and water supply facility was not available at their home. Majority of the respondents (95.71%) perceived that the water they use is of good/drinkable quality and there was no problem with the water they use, so far the quality of water is concerned. 100 percent of the respondents were engaged with livestock farming. Based on achieved results following recommendation were suggested: Meat/Livestock production in the target districts has no system and mostly the rural people supply the meat animals, where the health of the animals is not up to the mark. The livestock department must take measures to impart training to the livestock owners for achieving higher weight gain within short time by using concentrate feed in case the fodder and pasture feeding is inadequate.

Key words: socio-economic, spatial, livestock, Balochistan.

Introduction

Meat production is entirely associated with the production of livestock sector which is the single most important sector and can make an impact on the socio-economic condition of people and help in alleviating the rural poverty. The future of meat as an important nutrient source to a large part of the world population is indisputable and holds obvious challenges. Natural resources are becoming scarce and much more expensive, efficiency of resource utilization as well as productivity of meat is essential to meet these challenges (GOP, 2009).

The strategies for the livestock development cover aspects such as (i) livestock development led by the Public Private Partnership, (ii) National Economic growth, (iii) Poverty reduction, (iv) Food Security, (v) Improved service delivery in livestock and (vi) further develop opportunities for farmers in relation to cater needs of their livelihood (GOP, 2010).

Sheep and goat are the solitary source of mutton production in Pakistan, while buffalo and cattle, are the only sources of beef production. However, the population of cattle, buffalo, sheep, goat and camel during 2011-12 was

36.9, 32.7, 28.4, 63.1 and 1.0 million heads,(Table-1) while milk produced by cow, buffalo, sheep, goat and camel was 16.741, 29.565, 0.037, 0.779 and 0.829 million tons, respectively. The beef, mutton and poultry meat produced in the country was 1.769, 0.629 and 0.834 million tons, respectively. Of the total meat production in the country, the contribution of sheep is 7.74 percent, while a tiny contribution of 0.08 percent has been reported to total milk production in the country (FAO, 2010; GOP, 2012;).

World Meat Production

The world beef, pork and broiler production during 2009-2010 was 57017, 100780 and 71760 thousand tons. United States is the leading meat producing country in the world with 11889, 48890 and 15935 thousand tons of beef, pork and broiler production, followed by European Union i.e. 8935, 22060 and 12100 thousand tons; while Pakistan produced 1285, 1162 and 1772 thousand tons of beef, pork and broiler, respectively. These figures indicate that Pakistan is among the top ten meat producing countries of the world and ranks 9th after United States, European Union, Brazil, China Argentina, Russia, India and Mexico.

Meat Production in Pakistan

The contribution to total meat production in Pakistan by different species varies; and in total meat production of Pakistan (3,232,000 tons), beef production was 1,769,000 tons (27.30%), mutton 629,000 tons (29.02%) and poultry 834,000 tons (22.93%). In total beef production of 1,769,000 tons, buffalo contributes 51.53 %, while cattle shares 48.47%; in total mutton production of 629,000 tons, the goat shares 62.71% and sheep contributes 37.29% (GOP, 2012).

Table.1. Meat production for last 3 years.

Species	Units	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	2010-11	2011-12
Total Meat	000 tons	2728	2843	2965	3095	3232
Beef	“	1549	1601	1655	1711	1769
Mutton	“	578	590	603	616	629
Poultry meat	“	601	652	707	767	834

Source: Ministry of Livestock and Dairy Development, Government of Pakistan (2012).

Among breeds, Nari Master cattle is very promising meat breed of Balochistan, and in Sindh Red Sindhi and Thari cattle; in Punjab Sahiwal cattle and numerous indigenous cattle and buffalo breeds are reared for meat production purpose (Khan, 2003; Khushk and Memon, 2004). In goat, Beetal, Dera Din Panah, Kamori, Barbari, Chapper, Teddy, Pak Angora, Bikaneri, Kaghani and Khurrasani are reared in different parts of the country for meat as well as milk production purposes (Younas and Yaqoob, 2005; Khan, 2006). In sheep, Kaghani, Dumbi, Pak-Awasi, Balochi, Rambouillet, Kachhi and Kooka are popular local and exotic breeds reared for breeding and meat production purposes (Isani and Balouch, 1996).

At present, the meat production in the country is executed on informal grounds and the farmers adopt their traditional practices for raising meat animals and marketed through Beoparies/traders. These animal traders purchase meat animals from the producers and market these animals in the cities. The retailers (mostly butchers) after paying the price of the animals to these traders slaughter at slaughter houses. However, butchers themselves mostly act as the traders and always their agents explore the rural areas and look busy to deal with the rural people for purchase of their animals produced for meat production. Hence, the butchers dominate the meat market both in rural and urban areas. Animals sold in these markets are generally of good quality, however, diseased & culled animals are also presented, and some butchers/traders prefer to buy these cheap

animals because of no premium for quality. Slaughtering and meat marketing is a profession, which is inherent and passed through generations. Primitive techniques of slaughtering and meat marketing pass from generation to generation (Aslam, 2004).

With the passage of time, the patterns for meat consumption in the country have been changed; and in the recent past the chicken consumption has been found increasing regularly in the country. However, fast rise in poultry consumption during last two decades, prevalence of viral diseases such as bird flu has apprehended the production patterns and consumption too. In the year 2000, the share of chicken in total meat production was 49 percent, but later the share of poultry meat consumption came down to 39% in 2007. Most of this shift of people was towards mutton consumption which increased from 29 percent in 2000 to 36 percent in the year 2007. However, chicken is gaining back its lost share up to 45 percent (Gilani, 2009).

Balochistan Province

Balochistan province of Pakistan is well known for the livestock production, and is the origin of various ruminant breeds. On the basis of Livestock census 2006, the cattle production in Balochistan province was 2.254 million heads, buffalo 0.320 million heads, sheep 12.804 million heads, goat 11.785 million heads and camel 0.380 million heads; while the total livestock population was 33.991 million heads. However, the projected population for 2009-10 was 2.704 million cattle, 0.383 million buffalo, 15.396 million sheep, 14.142 million goats and 0.456 million camel. The animal population of various species such as: cattle, buffaloes, sheep, goats and camel followed an increasing trend up to 1997, but decline started from 1998 and this adverse situation persisted up to 2001. This was the period of severe drought in the province which resulted adverse effects on animal population.

Table-2. Balochistan livestock population (Million heads)

Particular	Cattle	Buffalo	Sheep	Goat	Camel
1	2.254	0.320	12.804	11.875	0.380

Livestock and Dairy Development Deptt; Govt of Balochistan Quetta.(2009-10)

From the year 2002, the population of almost all the animal species started increasing, but in the years 2004 and 2008 again a decline has been noted, but afterwards the population showed a smooth upward trend. The red meat production in Balochistan province of Pakistan showing an increasing trend and the total red meat production in the province during the initial year of analysis (2000-2001) was 193 million tons which showed a continuous increase over the years and reached 213 million tons up to the year 2009-2010 (GoB, 2010; GoP, 2012).(Table-2).

Table-3. Balochistan livestock projected population (Million heads)

Particular	Cattle	Buffalo	Sheep	Goat	Camel
1	2.704	0.383	15.396	14.142	0.380

Livestock and Dairy Development Deptt; Govt of Balochistan Quetta (2009-10)

Problem statement

Meat production is entirely associated with the production of livestock sector which is the single most important sector, can make an impact on the socio-economic condition of people and help alleviating the poverty in Balochistan. Sheep and goats are in every household; people are born herders and depend on flocks for their livelihood. Policies formulation lacks the attention towards traditions, cultural requirements, desires and needs

of the people who can exploit the existing potential of meat production in the province. Balochistan is the high potential area for meat production, particularly availability of pastures and rangelands for feeding livestock. Because of low rainfall and non-availability of canal water system in most part of Balochistan, the meat production potential is not being fully achieved. The availability of 90 % of the total province area is a great resource to meet feed requirements of sheep and goats. The northern rangelands are considered better in grazing, because of better average rainfall. They constitute 38 % of the total area but carry about 76 % of the total livestock in the province. Over-grazing, mismanagement, irresponsibility, lack of capacity of the related departments to manage pastures, overlapping jurisdiction and the disputed control of tribes and government over ranges, decrease in rainfall, depletion and degradation have resulted in reduction in the carrying capacity of rangelands. Balochistan 20 million animals are 6 to 7 times more than the % carrying capacity of the depleted ranges. Therefore, there is a lot of malnutrition, high incidence of parasitic attacks, and stunted growth of lambs, mortality and enormous losses. Lack of education and extreme poverty, generally in the whole area, and specifically in shepherds and flock owners are big impediments in providing vaccination, medicine and supplement feed concentrate to animals during winter season and in times of scanty rainfall. Sheep and goats are usually combined in herds because each has its own advantages. Goats are hardy and can better withstand feed shortage and low quality forage. Sheep are easier to manage, have bigger carcass for meat. Moreover, there are many breeds of cattle, some indigenous that also play an important role in the province's livestock sector. The most important aspect for the development of meat is the utilization of full potential of livestock. By and large revenue generation does not seem to be the prime motive behind livestock rearing. A major reason behind poor meat production per animal is the underweight animals, feed and fodder is in short supply during 7-8 months of the year, forage and fodder quality and its nutritional value is also limited. It is necessary to feed balanced supplementary diet for meeting the protein deficiency (Balochistan Development Statistics, 2008-09).

The above situation makes an uncertain situation regarding achievements of the target regarding meat production in the province. Such policies are needed to take solid steps for improving the situation at grass root level, so that the meat production can be sustained and targets set for future can successfully be achieved.

Objectives of study

The research objectives of this study are outlined as follows;

1. To explore the socio-economic background of the respondents.
2. To record yearly population of sheep, goat, cattle, buffalo and camel in Pakistan.
3. To suggest policy measures towards addressing the gaps between demand and supply in Balochistan province.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The purpose of this study was to record study the socio-economic spatial regarding livestock development in Balochistan: ways and prospects. Further, the study record perception and satisfaction level of respondents regarding the socio-economic spatial regarding livestock development. The survey research is a complete and systematic study, which is commonly used to solve particular problems. According to Kerlinger (1985), “survey research is a systematic, controlled, empirical and critical investigation of the hypothetical proportions about the presumed relations among the natural phenomena”. Samples of 70 respondents were selected randomly. To study the perception of respondents regarding livestock development in Balochistan and assessing the perception by using the questionnaires were designed with the help of research supervisor. The same language of researcher and the interviewees made the interview process easier and comfortable. The respondents were provided all the necessary knowledge without any reluctance or anxiety to build a trust between researcher and respondents. The interviews were conducted and responses were recorded on an already designed questionnaire. The data were organized and arranged in a coding sheet. The data were analyzed by calculating frequencies and

percentage. With the help of coding sheet, all the data were tabulated, summarized and analyzed with the help of SPSS, statistical computer software.

Socio-economic status of respondents

The socio-economic status of the respondents was assessed and the data (Table-4) indicated that 100 percent of the total respondents were meat producers.

Table-4. Distribution of respondents according to socio-economic status

Farmer's status	Frequency	Percent
Producer / Farmer	70	100
Total	70	100

Infrastructural public facilities

While enquiring the respondents existence of infrastructural public facilities for them which included existence of metallic roads, schools, health facilities, mobile/line-land telephone facilities and veterinary facilities for their livestock. The data indicated that majority of the respondents perceived that they have facilities of metallic roads (64.00%), school (78.57%), health facilities (72.85%), telephone facilities (67.14%) and veterinary facilities for their livestock (62.85%). This indicates that most of the respondents were having infrastructural public facilities and there was a minor population indicated non-existence of infrastructural public facilities at their door step.

Table-5. Distribution of respondents according to infrastructural public facilities

Infrastructural public facilities	Frequency	Percent
a. Road		
Yes	45	64.28
No	25	35.71
b. School		
Yes	55	78.57
No	15	21.42
c. Health		
Yes	51	72.85
No	19	27.14
d. Tele/Mob		
Yes	47	67.14
No	23	32.85
e. Veterinary Hospital/Dispensary		
Yes	44	62.85
No	26	37.14

Education level of respondents

On the basis of a sample size of 70 respondents, their educational status was enquired and the data indicated that yet the majority of the people (71.42%) were illiterate, while 7.14% of the respondents were having education up to primary school level and only 4.28 percent of the respondents could achieve for middle school level of education, while only 10 % of the respondents could achieve education up to matriculation and merely 7.14 % of the respondents could enter for college education. The situation clearly indicates that a high majority around 71.42% were either uneducated or they were having education below matriculation (Table-6).

Table-6. Distribution of respondents according to their education level

Education	Frequency	Percent
Illiterate	50	71.42
Primary	5	7.14
Middle	3	4.28
Matric	7	10
Intermediate	5	7.14
Total	70	100

Marital status of respondents

The respondents were also examined for their marital status and the data (Table-7) indicated that majority of the respondents (90%) were married, while the remaining 10 % of the respondents were still unmarried. This suggested that a considerable percentage of respondents were involved in meat production and marketing activity in the study areas.

Table-7. Distribution of respondents according to their marital status

Marital status	Frequency	Percent
Single	7	10
Married	63	90
Total	70	100

Distribution of respondents by their Ethnic groups

The respondents were also assessed for their ethnicity, generally represented by the language they speak and the data (Table-8) showed that majority of the respondents (57.14%) were Pashto speaking, while Brahvi speaking were 27.14% of the total sample size. However, 15.71 % of the respondents were from the Baloch communities. This indicates that red meat production and marketing was mostly operated by the Pashtoons, followed by Brahvi speaking.

Table-8. Distribution of respondents according to language spoken (Ethnic group)

Language	Frequency	Percent
Brahvi	19	27.14
Balochi	11	15.71
Pashto	40	57.14
Total	70	100

Family profile of respondents

While enquiring the respondents for their family profile, it was felt imperative to know the family composition of the respondents. The data suggested that majority of the respondents (31.42%) had families with up to 5 members, and 17.14 % of the respondents were responsible to manage families with 6-8 members; while 34.28 % of the respondents having 9-11 members and 17.14% of the respondents were found managing a large family setup of more than 12 members. Hence, the respondents composed a well-balanced sample size representing all classes of household families (Table-9).

Table-9. Distribution of respondents regarding total number of family members

Family members	Frequency	Percent
<= 5	22	31.42
6 – 8	12	17.14
9 – 11	24	34.28
12+	12	17.14
Total	70	100

Survey Report 2012

Family classification by gender

The family population was classified according to the age and gender of the family members and the data (Table-10) showed that the total population of respondent families was 633, out of which 139 (21.95%) were infants, 158 minors (15.8%), 199 adults (31.43%) and 137 old age (21.64%). Out of 139 infants (<5 years of age), 51.08% were males and 48.92% females, among 158 minors (5-15 years), 51.26% females and 48.73% males, among 199 adults (16-60 years), 50.25% males and 49.74% females, while in old age members in the families of respondents (>60 years), 56.99% were females and 43.06% were males.

Table-10. Distribution of respondents regarding family members by gender and age group

Age group	Gender		Total
	Male	Female	
Infants (<5 years)	71 (50.08%)	68 (48.92%)	139 (21.95%)
Minors (5-15 years)	77 (48.73%)	81 (51.26%)	158 (24.96%)
Adults (16-60 years)	100 (50.25%)	99 (49.74%)	199 (31.43%)
Old age (>60 years)	59 (43.06%)	78 (56.93%)	137 (21.64%)
Total	307 (48.50)	326 (51.50)	633 (100)

Educational status of children of different age groups

The data in Table-11 exhibited that out of 195 total boys in the respondent families, majority (47.18%) were educated up to primary school level, 14.36% could reach middle school, 5.13% achieved matriculation, 5.13% could reach college for higher studies, 4.62% were graduates, 0.51% had attended Madrassa, while remaining 23.08% were uneducated. Similarly, out of 175 girls in the respondent families, majority (52.57%) had only primary education, 14.29 finished their education after middle school level, 5.71% of the girls could complete matriculation, 1.71% entered college for higher education, none of them was graduate, 1.71% achieved Madrassa education and

remaining 42.00% percent were uneducated. This showed that a high majority of respondent population was either uneducated or they had education below matriculation.

Out of total 252 males above 16 years of age in the respondent families, majority (29.37%) were uneducated, 23.41% could complete Matriculation, 21.83% had only Middle school education, 8.73% could reach college for higher studies, 8.33% had only primary school, 5.56% were graduates, 2.78% had attended Madrassa, while remaining 29.37% were uneducated. Similarly, out of 263 female members more than 16 years of age in the respondent families, majority (56.27%) were uneducated, 11.41% had religious education in Madrassa, 9.89% of the females could reach only middle school level, only 7.60% were graduates, 7.22% could complete matriculation, 4.56% could only complete primary school education and 3.04% passed the intermediate. The results clearly suggested that a high majority of the females adults were either uneducated or having education below matriculation. Only below 20% of the female adults could complete high school (matriculation) level education.

Table-11. Educational status of children (5-16 years) and adults (above 16 years)

Gender	Education							Total
	Primary	Middle	Matric	Inter	BA	Madarsa	Uneducated	
Boys	92 (47.18)	28 (14.36)	10 (5.13)	10 (5.13)	9 (4.62)	1 (0.51)	45 (23.08)	195
Girls	92 (52.57)	25 (14.29)	10 (5.71)	3 (1.71)	0 (0.00)	3 (1.71)	42 (24.00)	175
Male	21 (8.33)	55 (21.83)	59 (23.41)	22 (8.73)	14 (5.56)	7 (2.78)	74 (29.37)	252
Female	12 (4.56)	26 (9.89)	19 (7.22)	8 (3.04)	20 (7.60)	30 (11.41)	148 (56.27)	263

Values given in the parentheses are row wise percentages

Distribution of respondents according to their income

(Table 12) shows the Total 70 respondents enquired during the survey for their monthly income, majority (55.71%) of the respondents had income up to 5000 rupees 18.57 %6001-10000 rupees, and 12.85 percent of the respondents had average monthly income from 10001 to 15000 rupees, while 7.14 percent of the respondents had their household monthly 15001 to 20000 rupees. However, 5.71percent of the respondents had their average monthly income from; more than 20000 rupees.

Table-12. Distribution of respondents according to total income of the household

Income /month (Rs.)	Frequency	Percent
<= 5000	39	55.71
6001 – 10000	13	18.57
10001 – 15000	9	12.85
15001 – 20000	5	7.14
20000 +	4	5.71
Total	200	100

Distribution of respondents for experience in livestock farming

The respondents were asked to perceive regarding time period/experience in livestock farming and the data (Table-13) indicated that majority of the respondents (58.57 %) had started livestock farming more than 10 years ago, while 17.14 percent of the respondents had started livestock farming during last 10 years, while 27 percent of the respondents out of 18.57 interviewees perceived that they had started livestock farming during last five years. However, a minor population of the respondents (5.71 %) did not respond to this effect. It was observed that most of the respondents were well experienced in livestock farming and only few of them seems to have little or no experience in the livestock activity.

Table-13. Distribution of respondents regarding time period of started livestock farming

Time period (livestock farming)	Frequency	Percent
Last five year	13	18.57
Last ten year	12	17.14
Above ten year	41	58.57
Not applicable	4	5.71
Total	70	100%

INFORMATION ABOUT HOUSE

Distribution of respondents according to their residential accommodation

The respondents were classified according to the type of accommodation they used to live and generally three types of accommodations were defined before the respondents as Pacca, Semi Pacca and Katcha houses to live. The data (Table-14) indicated that high majority of the respondents (74.28%) lived in katcha earthen houses and 15.71% of the respondents used to live in semi-katcha houses; while only 10% of the respondents used to live in pacca bricks made house. The situation clearly reveals an adverse residential condition of the respondents and still most of them lived in katcha/ earthen houses.

Table-14. Distribution of respondents according to type of house

House type	Frequency	Percent
Pacca	7	10
Semi pacca	11	15.71
Katcha	52	74.28
Total	70	100

Toilet facility at residential accommodation

The respondents were enquired whether their homes are facilitated with different types of toilets and the data (Table-15) showed that majority of the respondents (80%) had pit latrine at their residential accommodation, while remaining (20%) of the respondents had non-flush/WC toilet. This indicates that the conditions residential accommodation of the respondents was not according to the development of welfare facilities at the houses of general public in cities and towns.

Table-15. Distribution of respondents according to toilet facility

Toilet facility	Frequency	Percent
Non flush toilet / WC	14	20
Pit latrine	56	80
Total	70	100

Water facility at residential accommodation

The water is the basic need of human being and the respondents were enquired about the availability of this facility at their homes. The data (Table-16) indicated that majority of the respondents (55.71%) used tube well water and water supply facility was not available at their home. Similarly, equally 10 percent perceived that they had water supply facility, while 12.85percent respondents used well water for their household use. Some 12.85percent of the respondents used Karez water, while 8.57percent respondents have installed hand pump at their home.

Table-16 Distribution of respondents according to water facility

Water facility	Frequency	Percent
Hand Pump	6	8.57
Tube Well	39	55.71
Water supply	7	10
Karez	9	12.85
Well	9	12.85
Total	70	100

Water quality at residential accommodation

The water quality has always been an issue because poor quality of water is generally considered as the major cause of poor public health. The data (Table-17) showed that majority of the respondents (95.71%) perceived that the water they use is of good/drinkable quality and there was no problem with the water they use, so far the quality of water is concerned. However, some 4.28 percent respondents indicated the water they use is saline and the water quality is poor.

Table-17. Distribution of respondents according to water quality

Water quality	Frequency	Percent
Drinkable	67	95.71
Saline water	3	4.28
Total	70	100

Distribution of respondents by professions

The 70 respondents were assessed through interview for their profession and the data (Table-18) indicated that 100 percent of the respondents were engaged with livestock farming,

Table-18. Distribution of respondents regarding household members by profession

Profession	Total number of family members	Percent
Livestock farmers	70	100
Total	70	100.00

District-wise livestock density

Animal density in different ecological zones of Balochistan province was examined and the data (Table-19) indicated that the sheep was found in highest density (49.34±1.93%), followed by goat (39.29±1.26%), while cattle (3.32±0.20%), buffalo (1.27±0.12%) and camel (1.70±0.09%) were found in a low density. Similar trend was found in case of districts studied individually and sheep dominated the population, followed by goat, and cattle, buffalo and camel were composed a minor share in the total animal population of Balochistan.

Conclusion and recommendations

Socio-economic condition of the respondents plays an imperative direction in the income generation terming. The results reveal that 100 percent of the total respondents were meat producers. The data indicated that majority of the respondents perceived that they have facilities of metallic roads (64.00%), school (78.57%), health facilities (72.85%), telephone facilities (67.14%) and veterinary facilities for their livestock (62.85%). Majority of the people (71.42%) were illiterate. Majority of the respondents (90%) were married. While Brahvi speaking were 27.14% of the total sample size. Majority of the respondents (31.42%) had families with up to 5 members, and 17.14 % of the respondents were responsible to manage families. Out of 139 infants (<5 years of age), 51.08% were males and 48.92% females, among 158 minors (5-15 years), 51.26% females and 48.73% males, among 199 adults (16-60 years), 50.25% males and 49.74% females. Majority (47.18%) was educated up to primary school level, 14.36% could reach middle school, 5.13% achieved matriculation. Majority (29.37%) was uneducated, 23.41% could complete Matriculation, and 21.83% had only Middle school education, 8.73% could reach college for higher studies. Majority (55.71%) of the respondents had income up to 5000 rupees that majority of the respondents (58.57 %) had started livestock farming more than 10 years ago, while 17.14 percent of the respondents had started livestock farming during last 10 years. Majority of the respondents (74.28%) lived in katcha earthen house. Majority of the respondents (80%) had pit latrine at their residential accommodation. Majority of the respondents (55.71%) used tube well water and water supply facility was not available at their home. Majority of the respondents (95.71%) perceived that the water they use is of good/drinkable quality and there was no problem with the water they use, so far the quality of water is concerned. 100 percent of the respondents were engaged with livestock farming. Sheep was found in highest density (49.34±1.93%), followed by goat (39.29±1.26%). Based on achieved results following recommendation were suggested: Meat/Livestock production in the target districts has no system and mostly the rural people supply the meat animals, where the health of the animals is not up to the mark. The livestock department must take measures to impart training to the livestock owners for achieving higher weight gain within short time by using concentrate feed in case the fodder and pasture feeding is inadequate. Smuggling of meat animals particularly from Chagai/, Pishin and Killa Saifullah districts to Iran and Afghanistan may be checked.

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